

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH LITERATURE: ON THE EXAMPLE OF FAIRY TALES

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Abstract. In this article, the topic of fairy tales in Uzbek and English literature was compared and their impact on the mental development of the child was evaluated.

Keywords: folklore, heroes, child education, idea, goodness.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the spirituality, culture and wisdom of every nation is manifested through folk art. In particular, through fairy tales, which are an integral part of folklore, we can learn detailed information about the lifestyle, customs and traditions of peoples in the past. At the same time, fairy tales play an important role in the process of raising a child, expanding his worldview and making him a mature person. Because through fairy tales, you can encourage a child to do good and educate him in the spirit of love for the Motherland and respect for parents. Of course, this issue largely depends on the correct selection of fairy tales and thematic selection in accordance with the child's age and interests. Because the child elevates the protagonists of the fairy tales he hears to the level of an ideal person for himself, and in this case he tries to master the character and various actions of the protagonist of the fairy tale.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In today's rapidly developing age of technology, many mothers forget to tell stories, and children forget to read stories. However, it is not an exaggeration to say that the increasing number of bad vices such as theft, treason, treachery, betrayal of someone's rights, which are visible in society, is caused by not listening to fairy tales and not reading books at a young age. Because deep meaning is hidden in the content of each fairy tale and they lead the child to goodness from a young age. Therefore,

a child who grows up listening to fairy tales develops his worldview, his passion for learning increases, and as a result, he finds the right path in life.

Many studies have been conducted on the topic of fairy tales, and this topic was studied as an object of research in the 20s of the 20th century, and many scientific works on folklore were created during this period. In this regard, the researches of H. Zarifov, O. Madayev, K. Imomov serve as the main theoretical source in the study of folklore works.

In today's era of globalization, strong socio-economic relations are being established between countries, as a result of which peoples are exchanging ideas and learning each other's culture. In particular, folk tales are translated from one language to another, and their educational significance and themes are being analyzed. In her article, Julietta Alós explained the process of translating fairy tales, and Sh.U.Nurulloyeva explained the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek fairy tales.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

And Inge van de Ven explains how to concentrate while reading fairy tales. Of course, this issue is important for the correct understanding of the meaning of fairy tales and the correct conclusion.

K. Abdulloyeva analyzed English and Uzbek fairy tales from the linguistic, cultural and stylistic point of view. By studying these aspects, he paid attention to the linguistic, cultural, cognitive and comparative analysis of fairy tales. D.F.Khurramova and N.F.Ochilova commented on the specific characteristics of the leading characters in fairy tales and their cross-reference analysis in English and Uzbek languages.

All peoples of the world have fairy tales that have existed since ancient times and have been passed down from language to language for centuries, and they are a reflection of the dreams, life experiences, and thoughts of that people. It would be safe to say that our ancestors sent us messages about the future and their dreams through fairy tales. For example, through the "flying carpet" or "mirror globes" mentioned in fairy tales, we can see the image of "planes" and "televisions", without which it is difficult to imagine our life today. In addition, through the tale of "Susambil", it can be seen that in the past people lived by farming and animal husbandry and used animals in this process. In the fairy tale "Ur tokmok" it is

intended to give the impression of rich people and upper class people who are oppressing the people through the "Ur tokmok".

Tales in different languages may differ in terms of subject matter, but the idea, content and essence in them are described in the same or similar way. As an example, we can take Zumrad, the main character in the Uzbek folk tale "Zumrad va Kimmat", and Cinderella and Cinderella, the main characters in the English folk tale "Cinderella" and "Cinderella". The names of these characters are different, but the idea they want to convey to the reader is the same. In all three fairy tales, goodness is glorified and evil and evil in the form of stepmothers are condemned. It turned out that there are similarities in folk tales in terms of their creation in everyday life and very ancient times. But they differ from each other in the names of the heroes, the depiction of nature, their professions, and the narrative of events, and the lines of the national language and national spirit are clearly reflected in their description.

Scientists who study folklore say that many fairy tales are based on magic and miracles. That's why fairy tales usually start with "Once there is, once there is no...", which means that it is up to the listeners and customers of the fairy tale to believe or not. But fairy tales always attract everyone's attention with the story of the events and the skillfully arranged plot, so it can be said that the use of fairy tales in child education has a good effect.

At a time when Uzbek fairy tales mainly show credulity, simplicity, sincerity, honesty and a unique depiction of national traditions, English fairy tales are distinguished by their humorous spirit and wealth of humor. It is not for nothing that giants, fairies, sorcerers, creatures are mostly depicted in English fairy tales. For example, in the fairy tale "Jack and the Beanstalk" there is a story about a young man named Jack who fought with cannibals and saved himself and his relatives from them. In addition, in the fairy tales of Brothers Grimm and H.K. Andersen, we can see many characters, mostly people who lived in poverty and the rich and upper class people, and the honesty of the poor people and their lighthearted laugh at the rich people who are mean and torment the people at the end of the fairy tale. These tales appeared after capitalism and the bourgeois revolution and tell about the lives of people of that time, and the plot of the events in them is taken under a bitter laugh.

In today's era, it is very difficult to keep the young generation from getting addicted to information and communication technologies, to educate them to read and be sane. In this regard, it is important to tell fairy tales to children at an early

age, and here it is important to quote V.G. Gusev's opinion about fairy tales: "In society, in general, when the vices of human nature are not reflected in real life, they are fantastically reflected in fairy tales. will have a solution"[1]. Before telling a fairy tale, it is necessary to choose fairy tales suitable for the child's psychology, age, and nature. For example, if the fairy tale "Three clever boys" is told to children of 2 or 3 years old, it will be difficult for the child to fully understand the fairy tale and understand the plot of the events. It is also a mistake to read the English fairy tale "Peppa Pig" to children, because if you analyze the image of the main character "Peppa" in it, you can see the image of a girl who is very stubborn and does not listen to her father. It is true that he experiences interesting and cheerful events, and this may seem interesting to the child, but his character can also be quickly absorbed by the child.

It is worth mentioning that when a child is a baby, it is like a "blank sheet of paper" and they have a strong desire to explore the environment. In this process, stories help them develop their thoughts about the world and environment they are trying to understand, and help them get answers to their subconscious questions. Especially when the baby's language is coming out, if fairy tales are read to them, their speech will develop well. Because fairy tales contain more literary words than the words we use every day, and this is especially important for a child.

CONCLUSION

In short, fairy tales are a product of folk oral creativity and have made a unique contribution to the development of world literature. Tales provide information about the mentality, views, culture, socio-economic life of each nation. The heroes of English and Uzbek fairy tales and the meaning understood from them are the same, but if you analyze them in depth, you can see the differences in terms of the way of life and the views of the people.

REFERENCES

1. Abdulloyeva, K. (2021). Linguistic and stylistic analysis of English and Uzbek fairy tales. Scientific Progress.
2. Madayev, O. Uzbek folk art. Tashkent "Mumtozso'z" 2010
3. Zarifov, H. On the study of folklore and archeology materials. 2018.
4. Barziev, O. (2021). LYRICAL INTERPRETATION OF “I” IN THE POETRY OF ANBAR OTIN, DILSHODI BARNO AND SAMAR

BONU. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES, 2(06), 61-66.

5. Barziyev, O. H.(2021) Фарғона номи билан боғлиқ анъанавий поэтик туркумлар. НАУЧНЫЙ ВЕСТНИК. ФерГУ, 3(3), 108-114.

6. Barziyev, O. H.(2021) Traditional poetic series associated with the name of Fergana. Scientific journal of Fergana State University, 3(3), 108-114.

7. Barziyev, O. H. (2018). ANALYSES OF UZBEK POETRY AND TURKISH LITERATURE, IT'S FREEDOM AND NATIONALITY AT THE SECOND PART OF SIXTH CENTURY AND AT THE BEGINNING OF THE XXTH CENTURY. Theoretical & Applied Science, (7), 48-51.

8. Khurramova, daughter of Dildora Fazil, & Ochilova Naila Farmonovna. (2023). Comparative study of leading characters in Uzbek and English folklore. Journal of Pedagogy, 34(1), 145–151.

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